

Constituents of *Euphorbia pulcherrima* Willd.*

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The whole plant *Euphorbia pulcherrima* Willd. was found to contain the new triterpenoid esters germanicanyl tetracosanoate and germanicanyl behenate. Besides, germanicanyl acetate, epigermanicanyl acetate, 2-methyl anthraquinone, germanicol, epigermanicol, octacosanol and β -sitosterol have also been isolated from the plant.

EUPHORBIA pulcherrima Willd. (Poinsettia), a native of Mexico is a large deciduous shrub. In India it is commonly grown in gardens¹. The latex of the plant is reported to be poisonous to livestock. As no detailed chemical investigation on this plant has yet been reported we started work on the whole plant. TLC examination of the light petroleum extract of the whole plant showed a number of spots. On repeated chromatographic separation this extract furnished six distinct fractions. Fraction '1' yielded a substance, m.p. 84°-87°, $[\alpha]_D +22.5^\circ$ (CHCl₃) which imparted yellow colour to tetranitromethane and exhibited strong IR absorption at 1735 and 1175 cm⁻¹ indicating that it is an aliphatic ester. Analytical data suggested its molecular formula to be C₅₄H₉₆O₂. This was confirmed by its mass spectrum which showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 776. The NMR spectrum revealed that the compound is a fatty acid ester of a triterpene. The mass spectrum showed fragments indicating it to be the ester of germanicol with a C₂₄ fatty acid, namely tetracosanoic acid. The most intense peak in the spectrum was observed at m/e 204 (fragment c). The other significant peaks appeared at m/e 218 (fragment b), 205 (fragment d) and 177 (fragment e) which are characteristics of triterpenes of germanicol series². The fragment bearing the tetracosanoyl ester group also gave a peak at 557 (fragment a). The peaks at m/e 409 and 408 appeared due to the loss of tetracosanoyloxy group and tetracosanoic acid respectively from the molecular ion. The peaks at m/e 776 and 557 were accompanied by peaks of much lower intensity at m/e 748 and 529 suggesting that the ester group is partially formed of a lower homologous acid, namely behenic acid.

The above spectroscopic deductions were confirmed by saponification of the ester with 6% ethanolic KOH which resulted in the isolation of germanicol³ (m.p., m.m.p., $[\alpha]_D$; m.p., m.m.p., $[\alpha]_D$ and IR of acetate) and a mixture of fatty acids consisting mainly of tetracosanoic acid and a trace amount of behenic acid, which were characterised by their

methyl esters. Consequently, the triterpenoid ester mixture consisted mainly of germanicanyl tetracosanoate (I) and a trace amount of germanicanyl behenate(II).

Fraction '2' was further separated into two fractions. The earlier fraction on crystallisation from MeOH-CHCl₃ mixture afforded epigermanicanyl acetate⁴ (m.p., IR, NMR and MS) and the later fraction yielded germanicanyl acetate (m.p., IR, NMR and MS).

Fraction '3' on crystallisation from methanol yielded a compound, C₁₅H₁₀O₂ (M⁺ 222), m.p., 170°-71°. The various spectrometric data of the compound revealed that the compound is either 1- or 2-methyl anthraquinone. By direct comparison with authentic samples of both the methyl anthraquinones the compound was identified as 2-methyl anthraquinone⁵ (superimposable IR).

Fraction '4' was characterised as octacosanol⁶ from its m.p. IR and MS. Fraction '5' was further separated into two fractions 5a and 5b. Fraction 5a was identified as epigermanicol (m.p., m.m.p., Co-TLC and IR) and fraction 5b was characterised as germanicol (m.p., m.m.p., Co-TLC and IR). Fraction '6' was identified as β -sitosterol⁷ (m.p., m.m.p., Co-TLC and IR).

Experimental

M.p.s were determined in open capillary tubes in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. UV spectra were recorded in EtOH solns., IR spectra in nujol mulls and rotations were taken in CHCl₃ solns. unless stated otherwise. NMR spectra were recorded at 60 MHz in CDCl₃ with TMS as internal reference and mass spectra were determined at an ionising potential of 70 ev. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60°-80° and TLC was performed on silica gel G (Gouri Chemical).

Extraction and Chromatography: Dried and powdered plant material (800 g) was continuously extracted with light petroleum for 30 hrs. Evaporation of the solvent yielded a dark brown residue (26.2 g) which on chromatography over alumina (600 g) and successive elution with petroleum,

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 (I) $R = \text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{22}\text{-CO-}$

 (II) $R = \text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{20}\text{-CO-}$

 m/e 557: $R = \text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{22}\text{-CO-}$
 m/e 529: $R = \text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{20}\text{-CO-}$

 m/e 218

 m/e 204

 m/e 205

 m/e 177

petroleum-benzene mixture, benzene and benzene-ether mixture was separated into six fractions.

Triterpenoid esters: Fraction '1' (800 mg) eluted with light petroleum was rechromatographed on alumina column and then crystallised twice from *n*-hexane to give colourless granules, m.p. 84°-87°, $[\alpha]_D^{22} + 22.5^\circ$; IR 1735, 1175 (ester carbonyl), 715 and 728 cm^{-1} (methylene chain); NMR δ 0.73 (s, 3H), 0.84 (s, 6H), 0.91 (s, 3H), 0.97 (s, 6H), 1.02 (s, 3H), 1.10 (s, 3H), 1.32 (broad s, 45H), 4.5 (m, 1H) and 4.9 (singlet like, 1H) (Found: C, 83.41; H, 12.48; $\text{C}_{64}\text{H}_{98}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 83.43; H, 12.45%).

The purified product (200 mg) was dissolved in benzene (7 ml) and then saponified with 6% ethanolic KOH under reflux for 2 hrs. Worked up in the usual way when a neutral and an acidic fraction were obtained.

The neutral portion gave a white solid (90 mg) m.p. 180°-81°, $[\alpha]_D + 12^\circ$, IR 3250 (hydroxyl), 835 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond) identical with germanicol (Found: C, 84.42; H, 11.79; calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%). This was further characterised by preparation of its acetate m.p. 278°-79° (superimposable IR with an authentic sample).

The acidic fraction was esterified with CH_2N_2 and worked up in the usual way. The mass spectrum of the methylated product showed molecular ion peaks at m/e 382 and 354 suggesting it to be a mixture of methyl tetracosanoate and methyl behenate. The two esters were identified by comparison with authentic samples, of their GLC retention times.

Germanicyl acetate and epigermanicyl acetate: Fraction '2' (2.0 g) was separated into two fractions

'2a' and '2b' by rechromatography over AgNO_3 impregnated silicagel. Fraction '2a' (750 mg) on crystallisation from methanol-chloroform mixture yielded epigermanicyl acetate (350 mg), m.p. $136^\circ\text{--}37^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D -25^\circ$; IR 1740, 1240 (acetate carbonyl) and 840 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond); NMR δ 0.72 (s, 3H), 0.83 (s, 6H), 0.91 (s, 3H), 0.96 (s, 6H), 1.02 (s, 3H), 1.09 (s, 3H), 2.01 (s, 3H), 4.51 (t-like, 1H, $J = 7\text{ Hz}$) and 4.89 (s-like 1H). (Found: C, 81.85; H, 11.17; calc. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%). Fraction '2b' (1.1 g) on crystallisation from methanol-chloroform mixture afforded germanicyl acetate (570 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. $278^\circ\text{--}79^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D +16^\circ$.

2-methyl anthraquinone: Fraction '3' on rechromatography over alumina (20 g) followed by crystallisation from methanol yielded 2-methyl anthraquinone (150 mg), m.p. $170^\circ\text{--}71^\circ$; UV 207, 254, 327 nm; IR 1660 (aromatic carbonyl), 1580 and 708 (aromatic); NMR δ 2.51 (s, 3H), aromatic methyl, 7.71 (m, 4H, aromatic protons); MS (m/e) 222 (M^+), 207, 194, 165, 166. (Found: C, 80.98; H, 4.58; Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.06; H, 4.54%).

Octacosanol: Fraction '4' on crystallisation from acetone furnished octacosanol (500 mg), m.p. $82^\circ\text{--}83^\circ$; IR 3300 (hydroxyl), 719 and 730 (methylene chain); NMR δ 1.31 (broad s, 52H, methylene protons), 3.62 (t, 2H); MS (m/e) 392 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 378, 364, 350, 336, 221, 308, 307, 294, 293, 280, 279 etc. 97 (base peak).

Germanicol and epigermanicol: Fraction '5' on rechromatography over silver nitrate impregnated silica gel was separated into two fractions, '5a' (200 mg) and '5b' (600 mg). Fraction '5a' on crystallisation from methanol-chloroform mixture afforded epigermanicol (Found: C, 84.39; H, 11.80; calc. for

$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%). The identity of epigermanicol was further confirmed by preparation of its acetate, m.p. $137^\circ\text{--}38^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D -26^\circ$.

Fraction '5b' was further purified by chromatography and crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture as needles (370 mg), m.p. $179^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D +9^\circ$ identical with germanicol. (Found: C, 84.43; H, 11.92; calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%).

β -Sitosterol: Fraction '6' was further purified by chromatography. It was crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture as needles (600 mg), m.p. $138^\circ\text{--}39^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D -36^\circ$ identical with β -sitosterol (Found: C, 83.85; H, 12.26; calc. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 83.99; H, 12.15%).

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